

QUIZ**LAST NAME: ADU-TWUMWAAH****FIRST NAME: DEBORAH****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. KABIRU GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- In academic research, three kinds of questions are often asked by researchers to enable them to answer ‘so what?’ question of readers and provide a better understanding of the problem being researched. Which of the following answers represent the three questions? Tick the correct answer.**
 - Conceptual questions, physical questions and experience questions.
 - Conceptual questions, practical questions, and applied questions.**¹
 - Long questions, practical questions and short questions.
 - Short questions, long questions and experience questions.

- Which concept represents several particular conditions which are often added to support a research argument to make it relevant for easy acceptance by the research audience? Tick the correct answer.**

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 16.

- Warrant.**²
- Claim.
- Design.
- Hypotheses.
3. **In academic writing, there are two main citation styles available to the author to select from. Which of the following answers represent the two citations styles? Tick the correct answer.**
- Footnotes style and endnotes style.
- Notes style and bibliography style.
- Note-bibliography style and author-date style.**³
- Reference style and footnotes style.
4. **Which qualitative research tradition involves a detailed description of a setting and its participants, accompanied by an analysis of data for themes, patterns, and issues? Tick the correct answer.**
- Phenomenology.
- Case study.**⁴
- Ethnography.
- Hermeneutics.

² Turabian, 39.

³ Turabian, 87.

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 37.

5. **In reviewing literature for research work, it is important for the researcher to develop a working tool which consists of the categories emanating from the literature. Which of the following represent the researcher's working tool? Tick the correct answer.**

- Developmental framework.
- Empirical framework.
- Theoretical framework.
- Conceptual framework.** ⁵

6. **In qualitative research, four main areas of information are often needed to answer research questions and shed more light on the research problem. Identify the four main areas of information. Tick the correct answer.**

- Contextual, demographic, perceptual, and theoretical.** ⁶
- Conceptual, theoretical, empirical, and religious.
- Marital, employment, gender, and Age.
- Race, ethnicity, marital, and employment.

7. **In qualitative research, which data collection instrument serves as the major data collection instrument needed to understand the phenomenon under study? Tick the correct answer.**

- Questionnaire.
- Interview.** ⁷

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, 82.

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, 91.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 129.

- Secondary instruments.
 - Tertiary instruments.
8. **The European Union (EU) style guide demands celestial bodies and object like names of planets, moon, stars, etc., to be written with initial capitals because they are proper nouns. However, three of such celestial bodies do not take an initial capital unless they are specifically referred to as celestial bodies. Which of the following answers represent the three celestial bodies? Tick the correct answer.**
- The Earth, Moon, and Sun.**⁸
 - The Earth, Jupiter, and Mercury.
 - The Moon, Saturn, and Venus.
 - Venus, Mars, and Moon.
9. **Which punctuation sign is used to indicate an explanation, expansion, or qualification to a sentence? Tick the correct answer.**
- Semi-colon.
 - Full stop.
 - Colon.**⁹
 - Question mark.

⁸ European Union Commission Directorate-General for translation, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed., 2011, 15, http://ec.europa.eu/translation/english/guidelines/documents/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf.

⁹ European Union Commission Directorate-General for translation, 21.

10. Which EU's treaty allowed it to obtain legal personality in its own right and absorbed what used to be known as the EU community/ies? Tick the correct answer.

- Treaty of Lisbon.¹⁰
- Treaties of Rome.
- Treaty on European Union.
- Treaty of Amsterdam.

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¹⁰ European Union Commission Directorate-General for translation, 57.